

Local Governance, Local Democracy and Accountability Practices in the Federal Nepal

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Abstract

Over the years, Nepal has experienced numerous political upheavals and system fluctuations. Democracies are fundamentally accountable to their citizens because they allow them to elect public officials and, as a result, exert some degree of control and supervision over them. For this article, review of existing literature, reports as well as sector-specific laws and published related papers are analyzed. By focusing on local governance in Nepal, where citizens have little awareness of governmental decisions, actions, procedures, and outcomes, this essay investigates ways to address the difficulty of holding governments accountable. Based on devolution under federalism, the 2015 Nepali Constitution granted sufficient power and authority to local levels. After the new constitution was approved, Nepal changed from a unitary state to a Federal Democratic Republic in 2015. The second local elections in Nepal in 25 years were just held in 2022 whereas first elections were held in 2017. Overall, local governance under the current collateral system is not working properly. Various obstacles make it more difficult to achieve local democracy and inclusive governance, particularly in Nepal's rural and mountainous regions. For local development and grassroots democracy, the effectiveness of leadership appears to be crucial in dealing with local governance.

Keywords: Local governance, democracy, accountability, federalism, Nepal

Introduction

The pillars of democratic government are local governments. They actually serve as the citizens' governments. Local governments are the ones that exist close to home and in the community. Democracy is a system of the people, for the people, and by the people, according to one of the most well-known and widely-accepted definitions of democracy put forth by US President Abraham Lincoln (Haney, J. 1944). President Lincoln has positioned people in this instance as the center of democracy. The democracy's expansion and extension down to the local level is a significant way it has embraced its centrality. Some democracies have accepted the idea of federalism, while others have remained loyal to a unitary form of government (Suhrke, 2014). However, all of them have strived to deliver it at doorsteps of communities. In light of this, the ideas of democracy and local government have come to be seen as twin ideas that are both complementary and fundamental to one another. With representatives chosen by the local populace, local government is the governance of a certain county or area. The lowest level of government in most situations is the local government, which is a type of public administration (UK Government, 2016)

Since 1990 in Nepal, numerous of social and political movements have pushed for state restructuring to address concerns of diversity and growth and move toward a lower level of government. The Madhesh movement (2007) is one of them, as is the Maoist insurgency (1996–2006), Second People's Movement (2006), and others. For the purpose of reconstructing the state, the Constituent Assembly (CA) was established. The Constitution was ratified by CA in 2015 after much discussion. It designated Nepal as a "federal democratic republican nation," and the country enacted a federal political structure with three levels of government: the Federation, the Province, and the Local level. According to Nepal's 2015 Constitution, the federation, the provinces, and local levels are each given specific powers and authorities. It provisions local 'government'. The schedule-8 of the present Constitution includes 22 types of rights for the local levels ranging from local taxes to local level development plans and projects. The formation of local levels guarantees that citizens have access to services at their doorsteps. Success at the local level depends on effective government. Local governance is viewed as a structure and function in which various players come together to discuss current and future goals, choose representatives, and make decisions as a group. Marques (2013) argue that 'governance' embraces the capacity of a state to function effectively, and promote society's welfare and to deliver public services through the exercise of political power. Therefore, local governance is crucial for local development, delivery of social, and public services. However, the local level is still facing numerous problems despite the devolution of power.

Literature Review

Local government is an old idea that is also present in Nepal. However, over time, the nature and format of its practice have evolved. It has been a long journey from small village administrations to fully functional elected local governments. This path has seen significant changes in line with the worldwide movement, ranging from the administrative outposts used during the Kirat/Malla era up until the Rana government through decentralization, devolution, and federalism (Bhattarai, 2008). Local government in Nepal is currently modelled around contemporary, global democratic values. After a 20-year gap, Nepal's local government was restored through elections in 2017. It was the first election held in accordance with the new constitution. Mayors, deputy mayors, chairs, vice chairs, members of municipalities, and rural municipalities were chosen. The new local administrations have been in operation for two and a half years already. The municipal governments are portrayed in the new constitution as strong, useful, and independent governmental entities. However, there are still a lot of difficulties in putting the constitutional provisions into action. The local government serves as the people's closest form of representation in day-to-day affairs (Badal, 2019). The development and strengthening of local governments has become an increasingly popular method of serving the public, which is a compelling argument that is pervasive around the world. The forces of change that are promoting local democratization, in the opinion of International IDEA, have recently gained so much strength that it is now dangerous to fight them. Each and every small community now has a right to demand democracy. Political and administrative reforms aimed at decentralizing and bolstering local governance are now being implemented in more than 70 nations throughout the world (Sisk, 2001). Democracy in the true sense, therefore, is a form of decentralized system of governance. While viewing this phenomenon from purely ideological perspective, one has to consider the challenges facing the democratic governments of today – how their responsibilities have increased day by day along with the ever-increasing expectation

of the people in terms of efficient, quick and quality of service delivery. One of the logics was it is not possible for the governments in the center to carry out all of their responsibilities, nor be it practical. Therefore, instead of concentrating all functions at one level, the concept of devolving authorities has evolved. It underlines the need for functionaries at local level to carry out functions that need to be fulfilled at that very level. In other words, 'the process of handing over the functions of the central government to the local bodies is decentralization.' Analyzing from political perspective, a state can become efficient and effective if more, more rights are handed over to the local elected officials, and less and less rights are kept at the center. The works of public welfare and development can be better dealt by the local level in a fast and efficient manner. Governance through the elected local level officials would be in keeping with the principles of democracy and decentralization as well. It improves the state of answerability and accountability, as well as enhances public participation. It helps in local leadership development and maximum utilization of local resources meaning that by strengthening local levels the tenets of democracy can be taken to the people thus aiding to attain its fundamental goals.

The demand for accountability implicitly started in 1940s with the struggles for the overthrow of hereditary Rana regime and for the establishment of democratic rule. While some degree of accountability concerning the provision of public goods and services can be achieved in autocracies (Tsai, 2007), the notion is more broadly associated with the institutionalization of democratic rule (e.g. Taylor-Robinson, 2010; Herbert & Wilkinson, 2007; Goetz & Jenkins, 2005). Accordingly, the commitment of the Nepalese state to the ideal and practice of accountability received broad momentum after the restoration of democracy in 1990 in particular reference to the agenda on good governance. At the same time, the promulgation of the new constitution in Nepal in 2015 and the completion of the election for representative assemblies and governments at the local, provincial and federal levels have revived hopes for the bringing the country into the track of democratic evolution. The restoration of constitutional order and establishment of elected institutions in 2017 offer a new window of opportunity. Firstly, it allows the elected politicians to pursue governance measures in order to be able to deliver on their election commitments for development and prosperity. Secondly, it also provides the opportunity to adapt the measures already undertaken under the rubric of good governance, accountability or related themes.

Objective: The major objective of this article is to examine the practices of local governance, local democracy and accountability in the federal setup in Nepal. This article scrutinize the federalism with the constitutional sharing of power between the federal, provincial and local levels; understand the political commitment and revisit the policy, legal and institutional measures on local government accountability and their manifestations in local government settings to draw a conclusion.

Method: This article is based on the review of existing literature, reports and articles, which were undertaken based on secondary data and information. This article is analyzed the findings of previous research work most especially in a thematic approach. The review relies heavily on the secondary method of data collection other relevant documents published in national and international platforms.

Discussion

The Practice of Local Governance and Democracy in Nepal

Around the fourth or fifth century BC, an assembly made up of common people in Greece (Athens) is credited with establishing democracy (people's self-rule) (Raaflaub, 2007). The importance of the public's active participation in the collective self was highlighted by ancient Greek democracy. In terms of governance and government, Nepal has a long history. During the prehistoric era, Nepal was home to several little realms known as Janapad, including Videh and Kapilvastu (Nepal, 2055). In these principalities, choices were made jointly. In the past, the panchayat, a group of five people, was involved in preserving social norms. At that time, the utopian vision and moral education had a significant impact on governance. Three levels of government—the Center, Gram (Village Committee), and Tol (Block)—as well as local, self-government existed at the village level during the Lichhavi period, according to Regmi (1996). At each hamlet known as "Talaswami," a Talukdar Adhikari (authority chief) was also appointed. There were several tiny, autonomous principalities before the 1769 union. After the country's unification, minor principalities were incorporated into Nepal and the political form of government was centralized. The Limbu community's practice of Kipat, for instance, in the eastern hill region, where only Limbus had control in their territory, is an example of how the center did not interfere with any local sociocultural customs. However, the autocratic Rana dynasty controlled Nepal for 104 years, placing a strong focus on centralization.

The country was governed by parliamentary government after the revolution of 1950, with the monarch serving as the head of state. Although the king actually held the highest level of executive, legislative, and judicial authority, the concept of a legislature, an executive branch, and a judiciary was first proposed. The Constitution established five levels of government for Panchayat (1960–1990); these were the Rastriya Panchayat, five regional development regions, fourteen zones, seventy-five districts, and almost 4,000 local levels (village panchayats and municipalities known as Nagar Panchayats). After the first People's Movement in 1990, Nepal established multiparty democracy and decentralization was of greater interest to all. The Municipality and Village Development Committee (VDC) and District Development Committee (DDC) Acts, which were passed in 1992, likewise gave local government little financial authority. Later, in 1998, the Local-self Government Act was passed, which gave local governments some limited fiscal and resource-use authority but greatly favored the "center" in terms of budget, resources, and decision-making. The locally elected bodies, however, were impeded by the Maoist insurgency (1996–2006). Following the Second People's Movement in 2006, Nepal adopted the "federal political system" in accordance with the Interim Constitution of 2007. In 2015, the federalism became official. To handle diversity and improve sub-national territories, federalism has been proposed in Nepal. The social and cultural diversity of Nepal, inclusive development, and decentralization and the transfer of power and autonomy are the three angles from which the justification for federalization in that country must be understood (Sharma, 2014, p. 101). According to Article 306-n of the Nepalese Constitution, the local level consists of the District Assemblies, Municipalities, and Village bodies. In Nepal, the lowest tiers of government are the rural municipality and municipality. The institutionalization of a democratic and effective local government is the primary goal of the local level restructuring. The primary goals of the current local government are the efficient provision of public services to the local communities, the implementation of social and economic development

initiatives to improve the living conditions of the local populace, and the development of democratic leadership at the local level (Acharya, 2018a). To establish the "Singhdarbar" (Nepal's center of power) at every local level was the major goal of local governance. According to the constitution, there are 77 districts and 753 local levels in Nepal, comprising 6 metropolises, 11 sub metropolises, 276 municipalities, and 460 rural municipalities. Instead of "local unit," this Constitution grants "local government" autonomy. Federal, provincial, and local levels of government make up the Federal Democratic Republic of Nepal, according to Article 56 of the Constitution. The municipal level's authorities and powers are guaranteed under Schedule 8 of the Constitution. Local assemblies may pass required laws on the issues listed in Schedules 8 and 9 of the Constitution (as per Article 226). The same is true of Article 59, which states that local level bodies are permitted to create budgets for their respective levels using natural resources. Article 60 refers to the division of sources of income, contains a clause allowing for the imposition of taxes on subjects falling under their fiscal purview, and collects income from such sources.

The Essence of Accountability in Local Governance in Nepal

Since 2017, local governments (LGs) in Nepal have been in charge of overseeing governance and the provision of public services at the door level. To discuss the obligations of the LGs, important pieces of legislation have been passed. However, and as one might anticipate, their performance during the previous five years reveals a lack of institutional ability and sufficient human resources. It is also unfair that most sub-national governments do not have a system in place that rewards achievement, promotes accountability, and reflects transparency. This issue can be better understood by looking at the actual reporting of income and expenses. This section begins by explaining the constitutional underpinnings of the local social responsibility and then follows on to describe the primary strategies Nepal is using to achieve responsible governance. Accountability should be primarily thought of in terms of performance, finances, and justice (Niti, 2012). To put it another way, pertinent questions to ask local governments and individual officials include whether they performed successfully, how they handled public finances, and whether their choices were in line with expectations or any existing fairness and equity criteria. The following sentences list the strategies for promoting government accountability that are now in use and being developed (Dhungana, 2019).

The Local Government Operation Act, 2017 (LGOA) and Nepal's new constitution are currently the two main legal documents that shape accountability and are focused on the allocation and unbundling of functions for local governments. They also specify the legislative, executive, and judicial business that should be conducted at the local level. However, public oversight organizations like the Commission of Investigation of Abuse of Authority (CIAA) and office of the auditor General (OAG), provisions on the right to information and for good governance generally, and controls on corruption and public procurement. The primary focus of the Intergovernmental Fiscal Arrangement Act, 2018, is maintaining fiscal restraint at all levels of government. The National Natural Resource and Fiscal Commission Act of 2017 primarily addresses the creation of the commission, defining its mandate, and outlining the general guidelines for resource sharing. Three important institutions serve as the foundation for Nepal's public financial accountability: the Auditor General, a constitutionally mandated body, the Public Expenditure and Financial Accountability secretariat,

and the Public Accounts Committee of the parliament, which serves as a parliamentary oversight body. Public financial management (PFM) reforms are something the government is working to achieve. Social accountability (SAcc) procedures make up a final but significant accountability strategy that has been incorporated into various laws. These methods involve a variety of procedures, such as, for instance, public audits or budget tracking or evaluating public service (using a citizen scorecard) during public hearings (see Khadka & Bhattarai, 2012). In essence, they give local residents and beneficiaries the platforms and resources they need to speak out, look for information, and evaluate the success of initiatives, projects, public services, or facets of governance, management, or decision-making in public institutions. While a wide range of tools are accessible, it should be highlighted that some of them are now required for public organizations, particularly local governments (Dhungana, 2019).

Service Delivery of Local Governance in Nepal

In Nepal, the concepts of local government and local governance are considered important phenomena in the study of public administration; traces of their existence can be observed in Nepal since pre-historic times. Self-organized irrigation systems that farmers created to meet their needs for water and conflict resolution mechanism at the local level was a reality long before the current emphasis on federalism development emerged (Adhikari, 2021). Currently, a new federal democratic system is in place in Nepal. Through the expansion of high-quality services to the populace, this new framework can be supported and maintained. Since providing such services must be one of the pillars of Nepal's transformation in this context, the government of Nepal can help with the reforms needed to switch to the new system of federal, provincial, and local administration. (Association of District Development Committees of Nepal) (ADDCN, 2010). The Local Government Act of 2017 delegated various functions and responsibilities to local governments in terms of service delivery. Local governments in Nepal have given a variety of services, including vital registration (birth, death, marriage, divorce, and migration), social security payments, and support for local initiatives as well as those supplied under developed sectors. Agriculture extension, livestock services, elementary education, basic health services, rural roads/bridges, minor irrigation, community water supply, and sanitation are the seven services designed for local government in Nepal (NPC, 2010). Nepal still has problems providing citizens with effective public services. A sizable portion of the population still lacks access to fundamental public services. It is not unusual to come across individuals who have little to no experience with fundamental public services. Similar to this, the effectiveness and quality of the services still tend to be subpar. For instance, some healthcare facilities lack the necessary supplies and tools, as well as the medical staff needed to function there. Both the federal government (CG) and local level governments are responsible for providing services, and the poor status of service delivery has been a source of popular concern (Regmi, Naidoo, Greer, & Plkington, 2010). The central government's participation in service delivery is crucial because it is in charge of policy formation, financing, regulation, and actual delivery. However, the CG delivery has not been as efficient and successful as would be anticipated, due in part to a long chain of events from policy development to service delivery, a lack of local control, and a poor match between financial allocation and local preferences, among other factors. The importance of LBs in service has grown in recent years. Delivery has significantly risen. They have yet to be established as institutions of public service delivery, however (Regmi, Naidoo, Greer, & Plkington, 2010).

Problems and challenges

Local government is still not becoming successful and is dealing with many problems despite the devolution of power to local levels. When you consider how successful the local level is, it is a significant obstacle. In the case of significant choices, it appears that local authorities are still looking to the center for organization and guidance. Similar to this, many local levels are struggling with a lack of employees, and even where there is staff, there is often disagreement between the staff and the leaders. Similar to that, the development budget could not be used within the allotted time; only 12% of the overall development budget was used in the first half of the 2018–19 fiscal year in numerous local levels (Chaudhary, 2019). Primarily, there is yet no clear explication from the existing policy and legal framework about the full range of accountability relationships in which local governments are politically positioned vis-à-vis their electorate as well as provincial and federal governments and the public oversight agencies. The new constitution has envisaged local government units as largely autonomous entities, especially for the functions enumerated in Schedule 8 of the constitution, and are envisioned to stand along with other local, provincial and federal governments according to the principles of cooperation, co-existence and coordination. As a legacy of centralized rule in the country and as local capacity is yet to consolidate enough to serve constitutional obligations, elected leaders and civil service personnel are just beginning to come to terms with how they are expected to operate under the new constitution. Local governments are facing a various challenges nowadays, ranging from strong leadership to skilled staff to bad performance. There are gaps in technical and administrative knowledge and abilities, poor staff compliance with representative directions, insufficient attention to financial needs and limits, and slow programme and project implementation (Acharya, 2018b). Lack of rules, wasteful spending (primarily on personal automobiles for elected officials rather than public buses), and party preference over citizens are major impediments and barriers to local level success.

Summary and Conclusion

The system of local governance could potentially play important role in establishing, advancing and institutionalizing local democracy in Nepal. The insufficient experience and exposure, firstly, may be due to the existence of centralized and feudal influence along with underlying social structure. Secondly, it is endorsed to the limited resources and unfair practices of democratic norms and values. Thirdly, it may be due to the weak lobbying from and networking within the civil society actors. Fourthly, it may be due to the lack of understanding of local governance; and finally it may be due to the lack of honesty to fulfil the commitments amongst political actors and policy makers. According to Dahal (2017), an effective federal democratic republic requires good governance to function. Leadership, governance, and the institution/organization are all closely related to one another. Only when there is honest interaction between the leader and the public can the political institution, along with its structure and mechanisms that include devolution of power (in the federal context), service delivery system, and the roles and responsibilities of leaders, be effective and sustainable.

The three levels of government should all have a shared knowledge of the constitutional requirements. The constitution's co-existence, cooperation, and collaboration clauses should be adhered to in this case. There needs to be more effort put in. It will be difficult for the three levels to use the constitutional concepts of cooperation, coexistence, and collaboration because of misunderstandings about how to apply them. The

foundation of effective leadership and governance for the effectiveness at the local level is responsiveness (to citizens), transparency, and involvement. The practice of local levels in the federal context for Nepal is new, and roles and responsibilities of leadership in the current context are widened. Therefore, it will be beneficial to educate and train local-level leaders regarding power, authority, and function to increase the effectiveness of local governance. More effort will be required to create and institutionalize a clear and reliable framework for performance reviews and evaluations, which can then be used to inform local, provincial, and federal governments' planning and policy-making processes. The government should stress local level discussions and transparency procedures as the main foundations of enforcing local government accountability. The incentives for local leaders to interact with a variety of local constituents should be strengthened. These procedures would aid in strengthening and deepening democracy.

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